

Mechanistic Studies on the Bridge Cleavage Reaction of the Dinuclear Ethylenedibiguanide Complexes of Ruthenium-, Cobalt-, Chromium- and Rhodium(III) in Acidic Medium

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Acid-catalysed bridge cleavage reactions of four metal-ethylenedibiguanide (EDG) (metal = Ru^{III}, Co^{III}, Cr^{III}, Rh^{III}) complexes have been investigated in perchloric acid and for Ru^{III} complex in nitric and paratoluenesulphonic acids also. The Co^{III} complex reacts both via acid-dependent and acid-free paths, while other complexes by acid-dependent path only. Rate law for the Ru^{III} and Cr^{III} complexes is $k_{obs} = k_1 [H^+]$, that of the Co^{III} complex is $k_{obs} = k_2 [H^+] + k_3$ and for the Rh^{III} complex is $k_{obs} = k_4 K / (K + [H^+])$, where K is the equilibrium constant for protonation. The mechanism involves protonation equilibrium of respective complex, followed by a rate-determining bridge cleavage. Activation parameters have also been calculated. Order of reactivity of complexes is: Cr^{III} > Co^{III} > Ru^{III} > Rh^{III}.

Mechanistic studies on complexes containing one or more bridging ligands have been well-investigated^{1,2}. However, a number of complex compounds, as necessitated by the presence of various multidentate ligands therein, exist in dimeric or multimeric forms. Mechanistic studies on these complexes are interesting as the ligands form part of the 'bridge' resulting in dimeric form. Chromium(III) complexes of this nature have somewhat been explored. The kinetics of cleavage of the hydrolytic dimer of Cr^{III} was investigated in acidic solution. An equilibrium between the doubly bridged dimer and two single-bridged dimer gives rise to the acid-dependence of k_{obs} ³. Doubly bridged hydrolytic dimer of Cr^{III} gives the tetramer via three reaction pathways⁴. Base-induced cleavage of oxo-bridged Cr^{III} dimer have also been reported⁵. Ethylenedibiguanide (henceforth abbreviated as 'EDG'), a tetradentate ligand, when coordinates to hexavalent metal ions, forms dimeric form in which part of the ligand EDG acts as a bridge. Nevertheless, cleavage of such bridging ligands would be interesting. In the present communication, we report our findings on the acid-catalysed reactions of EDG complexes of Co^{III}, Cr^{III}, Ru^{III} and Rh^{III} and discuss the nature of the reactions of dinuclear as well as EDG complexes.

Perchloric acid was used throughout the study. In addition, nitric and *p*-toluenesulphonic acids (PTS) were also used for the Ru^{III} complexes to investigate the 'anionic' effect on rate. Nitric acid was also used to investigate the role of 'nitric oxide' complex which may possibly form during the reaction on the overall mechanism as Ru^{III} has a high tendency to form such 'NO' complex in presence of HNO₃⁶. PTS was used to investigate the role of a non-oxidising acid on the nature of the reaction.

The structure of EDG and its dinuclear complex⁷ with metal ions is depicted as follows :

Results and Discussion

Spectra, stoichiometry of the reaction and identification of reaction products :

Ruthenium complex : Reactions in presence of perchloric acid : The uv-visible absorption spectra of the dinuclear complex was insensitive to ionic environment, being similar within the experimental error in water and in 0.5 mol dm⁻³ solutions of sodium perchlorate. Fig. 1 shows the spectral scanning of an aqueous solution of 2×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ complex at 75° in the presence of 0.5 mol dm⁻³ HClO₄ and 0.5 mol dm⁻³ NaClO₄. The complex absorbed in the uv region only having λ_{max} at 289 nm ($\epsilon_{max} 2.52 \times 10^6$). After one day the spectra resembled to that of the diaqua complex [Ru(EDG)(H₂O)₂]³⁺, as formed by the hydrolysis of [Ru(EDG)Cl₂]Cl⁸. Isosbestic points were retained at 251 and 200 nm, indicating that only one species underwent hydrolysis. The solution after neutralisation was treated with ammoniacal copper sulphate solution, when red Cu-EDG complex precipitated out. One equivalence of the complex yielded one equivalence of diaqua complex and the ligand EDG⁹.

Reactions in the presence of PTS : On addition of PTS to the complex solution, absorbance increased at all wave-

lengths, particularly in the 240–280 nm region, where a significant change was noticed. This change in absorbance was due to formation of the protonated species. Product analysis of the reaction at 75° was made as in the case of HClO_4 . Again the products were diaqua complex and EDG with same equivalence.

Fig. 1. Spectral scanning of $\text{Ru}_2(\text{EDG})_3(\text{ClO}_4)_6$ in the presence of $0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ HClO}_4$ and $0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ NaClO}_4$ at 75° . $[\text{Complex}] = 2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$: (i) fresh, (ii) 1 h, (iii) 4 h (iv) 8 h, (v) 1 d and (vi) $\text{Ru}(\text{EDG})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{3+}$

Reactions in the presence of HNO_3 : On addition of HNO_3 to a complex solution, there was a change in absorption spectra with λ_{max} shifting from 289 to 300 nm. In presence of HNO_3 , a ruthenium complex shows the tendency to form a NO complex, which is very stable and cannot be easily substituted⁶. Change in spectral characteristics may be due to formation of such a NO species. The reaction mixture on standing at 75° for a day or two underwent little change in spectral pattern. It was loaded on to an ion-exchange column (Amberlite 120 in Na^+ -form) and eluted with a $3.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ NaCl}$ solution, after making the column free of NO_3^- . A pink coloured product was isolated from the dried up product of the eluted solution which showed an ir band at 1852 cm^{-1} . The product is thus an NO complex. However, its complete identity could not be made.

Reactions of the cobalt(III) complex in presence of perchloric acid: Spectral scanning of the complex ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) at 75° in presence of $1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ HClO}_4$ indicated that the absorbance decreased continuously at all wavelengths, ultimately becoming nearly zero after a day or two. The spectrum at this stage resembled that of the Co^{II} ion. EDG in the solution was estimated as before, but it was short of the stoichiometric amount. Probably a portion of the ligand was oxidised by Co^{III} .

Reactions of the chromium complex in presence of perchloric acid: The spectral scanning of the chromium complex ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) in the presence of $0.7 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ HClO}_4$ and $0.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ NaClO}_4$ at 50° is shown in

Fig. 2. The spectra changed with time ultimately becoming constant after a day or two. The reaction mixture at this stage was neutralised with KHCO_3 , cooled to separate deposited KClO_4 and passed through a cation-exchanger (Amberlite 120, 400 mesh in Na^+ -form). A light green portion was detected to be adsorbed on the column. The effluent was tested for the presence of EDG as before and was found to be positive. The resin column was washed with $0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ H}_2\text{SO}_4$, the eluent boiled, cooled and chromium was estimated as chromate¹⁰. The observed ratio of Cr : EDG proves that the light green complex adsorbed on the column is of the type $[\text{Cr}(\text{EDG})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{3+}$

Fig. 2. Spectral scanning of $\text{Cr}_2(\text{EDG})_3(\text{ClO}_4)_6$ in presence of $0.7 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ HClO}_4$ and $0.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ NaClO}_4$ at 50° . $[\text{Complex}] = 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$: (i) fresh, (ii) 1 h, (iii) 6 h, (iv) 1 d and (v) 7 d

Reactions of rhodium complex in perchloric acid Rhodium complex, much more inert than other complexes at $ca 85^\circ$ and in presence of $2.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ HClO}_4$ underwent aquation and in about a week's time yielded the corresponding diaqua complex; its composition and the amount of released EDG were determined as in the case of Co complex.

Rate law and rate constants

Reactions of ruthenium complex in perchloric acid The reaction follows a simple first order kinetics. A plot of $\log(A_0 - A_\alpha)/(A_t - A_\alpha)$ versus t , where A_0 , A_α and A_t represent absorbances at the start of the reaction, at the end and at time t , shows good linearity with zero intercept throughout the course of the reaction. Values of rate constants (k_{obs}) thus obtained between 68° and 80° and in presence of $0.1 - 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ HClO}_4$ are given in Table 1. A plot of k_{obs} vs $[\text{HClO}_4]$ also shows good linearity with zero intercept. Direct dependence of k_{obs} on acid concentration gives a rate law as

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k [\text{complex}] [\text{Acid}]$$

and $k_{\text{obs}} = k_1 [\text{Acid}]$ (1)

where k_1 is the second order rate constant for the reaction. Ethylenedibiguanide like biguanide possesses basic sites which in acid solution gets protonated, and as a result of protonation (due to inductive effect) the bond between the ligand and the metal ion breaks down. Cleavage of first bridge is rate-determining, cleavage of the second is a follow-

breaks down. This facilitates complete dissociation of the ligand EDG. The diaqua-complex does not undergo any aquation within the experimental acidity and temperature range. From the reaction stoichiometry and the rate law (1), the overall reaction taking place can be stated as

The diaqua-complex has a *cis*-configuration. Because of robustness of a tetradentate ligand complex, the possibility of conversion to *trans*-form is remote. Octahedral complexes with a teradentate ligand usually have a *cis*-configuration¹³.

Values of the second order rate constants as given by eqn. 1, are given in Table 2 along with activation parameters as obtained from Eyring equation. Errors are estimated from linear regression of data.

TABLE 1—OBSERVED RATE CONSTANTS ($\times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1}$) OF $\text{M}_2(\text{EDG})_2^{6+}$ WITH BRIDGE CLEAVAGE AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES*

Complex	Temp. °C	PTS (mol dm ⁻³)				
		0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	
M = Ru	68	1.30	1.51	1.74	2.23	
	74	1.48	2.09	2.90	3.51	
	80	2.23	3.19	4.05	5.66	
		HClO ₄ (mol dm ⁻³)				
		0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	
	68	1.24	2.03	2.13	2.66	
	74	2.00	2.55	3.55	3.83	
	80	2.48	3.55	4.26	5.59	
		HNO ₃ (mol dm ⁻³)				
	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5		
68				2.93		
74				4.36		
80	2.48	3.42	4.47	5.68		
	HClO ₄ (mol dm ⁻³)					
	0.25	0.35	0.50	0.75	1.0	
M = Co	63	1.62	1.89	2.74	3.51	4.19
	70	3.68	4.12	5.11	6.8	8.52
	75	6.39	7.99	8.44	13.7	16.20
	HClO ₄ (mol dm ⁻³)					
	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	
M = Cr	43	1.09	—	2.13	2.45	2.70
	50	2.13	2.66	2.98	3.48	4.26
	60	5.15	—	8.35	10.51	13.30
		HClO ₄ (mol dm ⁻³)				
	2.0	3.0	4.0	5.82		
M = Rh	80	5.01	4.0	3.8	2.84	

* Complex concn. = $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (for Ru, $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol}^{-3}$); ionic concn. for Co, Cr, 1.0 mol dm^{-3} , for Ru, 0.5 mol dm^{-3} , for Rh, 5.82 mol dm^{-3} ; error in k_{obs} is within $\pm 3.0\%$.

up process. EDG is a stronger base than bigH (for bigH, pK_1 is 11.5 and pK_2 is 2.95¹¹; and for EDG, pK_1 13.08 $\pm$ 0.2, pK_2 12.075 $\pm$ 0.05, pK_3 2.9 and pK_4 1.8¹², all at 32°). In the coordinated form although these pK values are different, however, the order remains the same. It is the most basic point that gets protonated and as a result of protonation, bridge cleavage takes place. Formation of $[\text{Ru}(\text{EDG})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{3+}$ as a reaction product indicates that EDG ligand that binds two nuclei together breaks down as a result of protonation. As one 'bridge' breaks down, the other one being unable to bear the strain to keep two nuclei together,

TABLE 2—RATE CONSTANTS AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS OF $\text{M}_2(\text{EDG})_2^{6+}$ COMPLEX IONS VIA ACID-DEPENDENT (k_H , $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$) AND ACID-FREE (k_0) PATHS (s^{-1} , FOR Co^{III} ONLY)

Complex	Acid	Temp. °C	k_H	k_0	$\Delta H^\ddagger$	$\Delta S^\ddagger$
					kJ mol ⁻¹	JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
Ru	PTS	68	4.5 $\pm$ 0.1		77 $\pm$ 5	- 105 $\pm$ 10
		74	7.0 $\pm$ 0.2			
		80	11.2 $\pm$ 0.3			
	HClO ₄	68	5.4 $\pm$ 0.2		59 $\pm$ 4	- 155 $\pm$ 15
		74	8.3 $\pm$ 0.3			
		80	11.3 $\pm$ 0.4			
	HNO ₃	68	5.8 $\pm$ 0.2		57 $\pm$ 4	- 159 $\pm$ 20
		74	8.4 $\pm$ 0.2			
		80	11.3 $\pm$ 0.4			
Co	HClO ₄	63	2.4 $\pm$ 0.07	1.33 $\pm$ 0.04	136 $\pm$ 6	70 $\pm$ 8
		70	5.8 $\pm$ 0.08	2.40 $\pm$ 0.04	79 $\pm$ 5	- 105 $\pm$ 10
		75	12.9 $\pm$ 0.12	3.50 $\pm$ 0.07		
	HClO ₄	43	3.8 $\pm$ 0.2		79 $\pm$ 6	- 84 $\pm$ 12
		50	6.4 $\pm$ 0.2			
	60	16.6 $\pm$ 0.3				
Rh	HClO ₄	80	2.53 $\pm$ 0.14		—	—

Reactions in presence of PTS: The whole course of the reaction in presence of PTS is also similar to that in HClO₄. Ruthenium(III) in presence of an oxidising acid like HClO₄, may convert partially to higher oxidation states. However, similarity of the reaction in presence of both HClO₄ and PTS shows that no such conversion to higher oxidation

where both k'_1 and k'_{-1} are nearly equal so that at equilibrium both the species I and II are present. From reaction sequence (6),

$$\text{Rate} = K_4[III] = \frac{k_4 K}{K + [H^+]} [\text{complex}] \quad (7)$$

$$\text{So, } 1/k_{\text{obs}} = 1/k_4 + [H^+]/k_4 K \quad (8)$$

From a plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs [acid], the values of k_4 (reciprocal of intercept) is obtained as $(8.69 \pm 0.43) \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and equilibrium constant K (ratio of gradient to intercept) as $(4.6 \pm 0.3) \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Conclusion :

All the metal-EDG complexes included in the present study have their own reaction rate laws. The Co complex reacts both by acid-catalysed and acid-free paths. Ru and Cr react by acid-catalysed path only and for the Rh complex an equilibrium between the protonated and the non-protonated form takes part in the aquation reaction giving a non-linear relation between k_{obs} and [acid]. The similar rate laws and rate constant values of Ru complex in different acids show that there is no anionic effect of rate on this complex. At a particular temperature chromium complex is probably most reactive of all. For both the biguanide and substituted biguanide complexes, Cr^{III} complexes show a greater reactivity. The reactivity order of all the complexes in the presence of HClO₄ is : Cr^{III} > Co^{III} > Ru^{III} > Rh^{III}. The metal biguanide complexes also show a similar reactivity order¹⁶. In chelate-bridged complexes studied herein, bridge cleavage takes place by protonation at a basic centre. Bridge cleavage at one point of attachment results in the complete dissociation of the EDG chelates. Kinetically the first bridge is somewhat more stable than the others so that with cleavage of this bridge other bridging arms also get dissociated. Order of reactivity of these metal complexes shows similar trend as observed in complexes of these metal ions with other ligands.

Experimental

Dinuclear EDG complexes of Co^{III}¹⁷, Cr^{III}¹⁷, Ru^{III}¹⁸ and Rh^{III}¹⁸ were prepared according to literature methods. The complexes were characterised by elemental analysis.

Perchloric, nitric and PTS acids (AnalaR) were diluted to desired molarities with conductivity water. Solutions of sodium nitrate, sodium perchlorate and sodium *p*-toluenesulphonate of desired strengths were also prepared in con-

ductivity water and standardised by ion-exchange salt splitting method by passing through a cation-exchange resin bed (Amberlite 120: H⁺ form) and titrating the corresponding acid in the effluent with standard NaOH solution. Ionic strength of each experimental solution was adjusted to appropriate strength with sodium salt of respective acids.

An ECIL spectrophotometer was used for monitoring kinetic runs and also for spectral measurements. Reactions were carried out in stoppered Jena volumetric flasks placed in a thermostat maintained at the desired temperature. Sample quenching technique was adopted for absorbance measurements at suitable time intervals of each complex. All kinetic experiments were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions.

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